

EARTH SCIENCES

GEOLOGICAL EXPLORATION METHODS FOR STRATEGIC METALS IN THE USA: MODERN APPROACHES AND TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract

The article analyzes modern methods of geological exploration for strategic metals, such as lithium, cobalt, and rare-earth elements, used in the USA. Airborne geophysics, satellite exploration, and geochemical methods, which have developed significantly in recent decades, are discussed. Their advantages, limitations, and potential integration for enhancing exploration accuracy and efficiency are assessed. The application of these methods in different geological conditions is presented, highlighting their role in effective exploration and evaluation of critical resource deposits.

Keywords: *geological exploration, strategic metals, airborne geophysics, satellite exploration, geochemistry, technologies.*

Introduction

The manufacturing of high technologies, industry and energy now creates a growing demand for strategic metals such as lithium, cobalt, rare earth elements (REEs) and niobium. They are of vital significance in the production of batteries, electronics, defense systems and renewable energy sources. Domestically stable sources of these strategically vital resources are becoming the United States priority. Specifically, particular focus is being assigned to improving exploration technology for the successful discovery of new deposits as well as reassessment of deposits already discovered.

The objective of this research is to study modern technologies of geological prospecting of strategic metals used in the United States. Special consideration is provided for aerogeophysical, satellite and geochemical techniques because they were comprehensively developed during the last decades and naturally combined with computer technology. These techniques possess significant potential for improvement of the spatial analysis process and prediction of ore-bearing areas.

The research considers theoretical matters, and not only their implementation in practice for different geological conditions, but also offers a means to establish how they perform and develop.

Main part. Theoretical foundations of geological exploration of strategic metals

Strategic metal geological exploration is that aspect of geological exploration which concerns itself with the exploration and estimation of deposits of those elements that are of extremely high economic and technological importance but have a relatively restricted distribution in the Earth's crust. Strategic metals are federally identified as critical materials for national security and technological self-sufficiency in the United States. Such metals are, first of all, lithium, cobalt, vanadium, graphite, REEs, and platinum group metals. The peculiarity of their exploration is the need to take into account not only geological, but also technological and economic factors determining the possibility of industrial development of deposits (fig. 1).

Figure 1. U.S. Geological Survey data on mineral areas, mines, and mineral deposits [1]

From a theoretical perspective, geological prospecting rests on the theory of mineralogical and geochemical specialization, which states that strategic ore bodies are formed under certain geodynamic conditions, including active continental margins, intraplate rift zones or old cratons. These rock masses are usually connected with certain types of magmatism and metamorphism, which are the reasons behind rare element accumulation in the products of ore formation. Effective exploration is thus predicated on **employing an integrated methodology** that includes the use of remote sensing, geophysics, and geochemistry methods to locate subtle but significant evidence of ore content [2].

One of the most important factors in constructing predictive models is **regional metallogenic typing**, used to determine the possible mineralization of areas. Typification involves the examination of the structure and evolution history of the region's geological development, taking into account the cyclical nature of magmatic and metamorphic processes. It is also supplemented by the use of geostatistical methods and machine learning elements for systematization and interpretation of spatial data on the rock structure, physical field and geochemical ones.

Advances in aerogeophysical exploration methods

The aerogeophysical method is the most effective among the geological prospecting methods of strategic metals, allowing you to survey large regions very rapidly at low expense. It is a method involving aerial platforms for the execution of geophysical measurements, i.e., magnetic, gravitational, and electromagnetic prospecting. Aerogeophysics allows the detection of anomalies associated with the occurrence of ore bodies, which are difficult to detect by surface methods. Its greatest advantage is that the aerogeophysical method is a very useful tool and is capable of defining potential fields to pursue further detailed exploration.

Application of aeromagnetic and aerogravimetric surveys provides unique information concerning the

structure of the Earth's crust. The anomalies in magnetism of magmatic and metamorphic origins provide prediction for the location of metal deposits, i.e., nickel, cobalt, and REEs. Ore bodies depth and dimension are indicated through gravimetric surveys. Such technologies provide recognition of the anomalies produced from fluctuations of the density of the rocks, something that is very vital while estimating deep deposits of strategic metals.

Electromagnetic methods, however, utilize differences in the conductivity of the earth's layers, which can be used to good effect when exploring for metals such as lithium and graphite. This data is collected through air-sensing methods by way of specialized equipment that transmits information to ground stations. Modern aerogeophysical survey systems are able to cover areas of several thousand square kilometers in a single survey, and they are thus highly useful for large-scale exploration in difficult geological environments. An example is the Kuskokwim aerial electromagnetic survey in Alaska in 2024 that covered around 2,037 square kilometers in a single block [3].

Remote sensing and satellite technologies in geological prospecting

Outer space exploration and remote sensing are increasingly becoming a part of modern geological exploration instruments, including prospecting and monitoring strategic deposits of metals. The methods allow for acquisition of data on the Earth's surface geological structure and chemical composition with high precision and in broad scale. Effective mapping of the territory and detection of anomalies related to ore objects, such as lithium, cobalt, and REEs, are provided by these methods.

Satellite intelligence is based on the use of information from various types of satellites – optical, radar, and hyperspectral. Use of hyperspectral imagery enables a person to obtain spectral information that can precisely determine the surface mineralogical composition and locate geochemical anomalies [4]. This technique is highly useful in prospecting for rare earth and

particularly lithium deposits since hyperspectral images allow you to not only map minerals, but also their concentration in the ground. For example, in the United States, **Sentinel-2** satellite imagery data are already utilized in monitoring natural resource change and marking mineralization features.

Remote sensing is employed to acquire data on terrain, temperature anomalies, humidity, and other geophysical parameters, which assist in the estimation of deep processes and the localization of exploration areas of the most promising prospects. Present satellite technologies provide for real-time observation, significantly increasing the effectiveness of decision-making in field exploration. For example, using **RADARSAT-2** satellites for radar sensing allows you to research changes in the structure of the soil and topography, which is valuable information for the planning of drilling and geochemical research.

Geochemical methods in the exploration of critical minerals

Geochemical methods of geological prospecting are an important tool for assessing the content of strategic metals in natural objects, such as soils, waters, vegetation, and sediments. Geochemical methods are based on the analysis of chemical elements concentrations and isotope ratios and allow for the identification of anomalies concerning the occurrence of ore objects and assessment of prospects of territory for exploration. One of the main advantages of geochemical methods is that they have the ability **to detect weak anomalies** that can indicate the presence of ore bodies at high depths.

There are several types of geochemical studies, including direct (analysis of soil and water samples) and

indirect (e.g., bioindicators). Geochemical techniques are particularly applicable in areas with a saturated hydrology and soil system, where trace heavy metals might be due to element migration in aquifers or in the crust. In particular, using vegetation analysis to identify the presence of metals such as lithium or cobalt can show where these metals are likely to accumulate in biomass. It has been shown through research that for some metals, such as rare earths, vegetation will have higher concentrations than in the surrounding soils. In 2024, the **Pohlia flexuosa** moss was studied within the black shale zones and discovered that it held REEs amounts of up to 86.2 ± 64.3 mg / kg, even though the soil itself was 327 ± 91.8 mg / kg in concentration. That shows, moss can accumulate the REEs quantities that are comparable or even surpass the amount that exists in neighboring soil [5].

Geochemical mapping also involves the use of various sampling techniques, such as manual drilling or probing, to obtain soil samples at various depths. Modern methods make it possible to perform complex analysis using highly sensitive instruments, such as mass spectrometers and atomic absorption spectrophotometers, which increases the accuracy of concentration determination [6].

Comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of methods

A comparative assessment of various methods of geological exploration of strategic metals allows us to identify their advantages and limitations depending on the geological conditions and research goals. Each method has its own characteristics that make it more or less effective in different contexts (table 1).

Table 1.

Comparative assessment of geological exploration methods

Method	Advantages	Limitations
Remote sensing	Rapid coverage of large areas, identification of structural and geomorphological anomalies.	Requires ground verification, sensitive to weather conditions.
Airborne geophysics	High sensitivity, wide-area coverage, suitable for concealed structures.	High cost, limited resolution at shallow depths.
Geochemical mapping	Precise anomaly localization, quantitative estimation of element concentrations.	Requires dense sampling, dependent on geological conditions.
Vegetation analysis (Biogeochemistry)	Detection of hidden anomalies, environmentally friendly, low fieldwork cost.	Limited applicability, affected by seasonality and vegetation type.
Surface geophysics (magnetometry, electromagnetic surveys)	Effectively detects subsurface structures, no drilling needed at early stages.	Sensitive to interference, requires professional interpretation.

For example, aerogeophysical surveys can cover vast areas within a short period but require high accuracy and experienced data interpretation, especially in poor geological conditions. Satellite intelligence and remote sensing, however, offer good chances for monitoring of large areas based on orbital platform data but are accuracy limited by the sensor resolution used and by the complexity of hyperspectral image analysis [7].

Geochemical methods, while being very precise in locating the composition of rocks and grades of key metals, require cumbersome field work in sample collection and further lab processing. These are the reasons why they are more time- and manpower-consuming than satellite and aerogeophysical methods. Yet, all

these disadvantages aside, geochemistry remains a leading instrument in seeking for weak anomalies, especially under poor abundance conditions of ore bodies.

The integration of various methods, e.g., an integration of geochemical mapping and aerogeophysics, can enhance geological exploration significantly. Aeromagnetic information, e.g., can be used for initial targeting of anomalies, followed by geochemical investigation that provides detailed information regarding the metal content in such anomalies. This allows not only precision, but also cost optimization, since it avoids unnecessary expensive drilling operations [8].

Thus, the effectiveness of exploration methods is set by the arrangement of their potential and by the features of the examined region. It must be added that the highest outcome is reached by applying integrated methods, by which the accuracy of the forecast can grow hundreds of times and the economic efficiency of the entire process of exploration can grow many times.

Conclusion

Modern methods of exploration employed on United States strategic metals, including aerogeophysics, satellite surveillance, and geochemical exploration are accountable for effective search and estimation of huge resources deposits. All these methods, being strong in their own right, are highly effective and accelerate the process of exploration to greater levels of accuracy and precision. Particularly, satellite and aerogeophysics can scan extremely large distances at a high rate. Still, geochemical survey provides a very high resolution of the chemical composition of the ore and facilitates even weak anomalies detection.

But to be as efficient as possible, these methods need to be combined, which not only improves precision, but also reduces the cost of exploration. In the coming years, increasing numbers of innovations and marriages of technologies and the implementation of new analytical techniques such as artificial intelligence and machine learning will introduce even more efficiency and precision in the exploration of strategic metals.

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